

Developing metrics and instruments to evaluate citizen science impacts on the environment and society

EC Horizon-2020 Grant Agreement number 824711

Call: H2020-SwafS-2018-2020 (Science with and for Society)

Topic: SwafS-15-2018-2019

Type of action: RIA

UPDATE to Deliverable 4.5 - Comprehensive Evaluation Report

Delivery Year: 2021

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824711.

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Purpose of this Document

Following the completion of Deliverable D4.5 (Wheatland et al., 2022) several updates were made to the Impact Monitoring Journeys (IMJs) and Impact Monitoring Strategies (IMS) of the MICS case studies. These specifically related to changes in the Outfall Safari, Marzenego and Carasuhat case studies and are outlined in this document.

Part A: Standardising the Impact Journey Maps of the MICS Case Studies

- A review of the Impact Journey Maps (IJM) created for each of the MICS case studies was conducted to identify similar concepts shared between the case studies and to standardise them.
- Minor changes to the wording of elements in the IJMs were made, while avoiding significant deviation from original concepts.
- A total of 100 individual elements (*Activities, Outputs, and Long-term and Short-term Impacts*) were identified.
- Table 1 lists each element (*Activities, Outputs, and Long-term and Short-term Impacts*) and indicates which of the case studies they relate to.

Table 1. IJM items identified in the MICS case studies.

Item Type	IJM Item Number	IJM Item	Outfall Safari	Riverfly Monitoring Initiative	Marzenego River NBS project	Creek Rákös Citizen Science Project	Carasuhát Wetland NBS project
Activities	1	Secure resources	x				
	2	Engage local stakeholder groups	x	x	x	x	x
	3	Monitoring methodology / activities defined	x	x	*Output	*Output	*Output
	4	Conduct monitoring activities	x	x	x	x	x
	5	Project planning	x				
	6	Reporting to regulatory agency	x	x			
	7	Feedback / follow up to citizen scientists	x	x			
	8	Future development	x				
	9	Engage local schools			x		
	10	Adaptation and validation of methods			x		
	11	Data processing & visualisation			x	x	x
	12	Outreach & awareness raising			x		x
Outputs	13	Monitoring methodology / activities defined	*Activity		x	x	x
	14	Increased involvement in citizen science - cascade effect	*Short-term impact	*Short-term impact			x
	15	Baseline dataset established / improved data coverage			x	x	x
	16	Increased awareness & acceptance of citizen scientists				x	
	17	More suitable and reliable methods developed			x		
	18	Early warning system developed			x		
	19	Increased scientific evidence supporting effectiveness of NBS			x		
	20	Improved citizen scientist understanding of data			x		
	21	Volunteers trained and equipped	x	x	x		
	22	Network between different schools established			x		
	23	Pollution events identified & reported to EA)		x			
	24	Data checked by Riverfly group coordinator (LCSP)		x			
	25	Extended Riverfly Methodology developed		x			

Item Type	IJM Item Number	IJM Item	Outfall Safari	Riverfly Monitoring Initiative	Marzenego River NBS project	Creek Rákos Citizen Science Project	Carasuhát Wetland NBS project
	26	Increased publicity and PR for project		x		x	
	27	Funding sources identified	x				
	28	Volunteers engaged via environ. NGOs	x				
	29	Other groups from general public engaged	x				
	30	Statutory agencies engaged	x				
	31	Local authorities engaged	x				
	32	Water companies engaged	x				
	33	Identification of polluting outfalls (Incl. the non-significant ones)	x				
	34	Analysis of survey results	x				
	35	Feedback provided to volunteers	x				
	36	Expansion of project scope	x				
	37	Disseminate approach	x				
	38	Coordinating with other citizen science initiatives	x				
Short-Term Impacts	39	Stronger community feeling / sense of place	x				
	40	Upskilling	x				
	41	Locations of misconnections investigated	x				
	42	Targets for mitigating polluting outfalls met	x				
	43	Outfalls prioritised	x				
	44	Political pressure on local MPs, etc. and water companies and EA (by citizen scientists and wider public)	x				
	45	Application of Outfall Safari method in other urban areas	x				
	46	Improved mental and physical health of volunteers	x	x			
	47	Increased collaboration between different schools			x		
	48	Increased involvement in citizen science - cascade effect	x	x			*Output
	49	Opportunistic pollution events reduced		x			
	50	Pollution source identified and remedied		x			
	51	Improved scientific knowledge		x	x		
52	Application of Extended Riverfly methodology by other Riverfly groups		x				

Item Type	IJM Item Number	IJM Item	Outfall Safari	Riverfly Monitoring Initiative	Marzenego River NBS project	Creek Rákos Citizen Science Project	Carasuhat Wetland NBS project
	53	Enhanced citizen science knowledge	x	x	x		x
	54	Improved citizen consultation in decision making by local authorities					x
	55	Baseline data used for management plans/policy					x
	56	Wider awareness of environmental issues			x		
	57	Demand side growth: Increased number of eco-tourists / visitors to wetlands					x
	58	Business opportunities	*Long-term impact				x
	59	Increased capacity within the DDBRA for data management					x
	60	Shared understanding of how to run effective citizen science activities	x				x
	61	Improved relationships among stakeholders	x	x	x		
	62	Increased cooperation and/or collaboration between stakeholders			x	*Long-term impact	x
	63	Enhanced environmental databases / data coverage		x	x		
	64	Early identification of problems			x		
	65	Increased public awareness and knowledge of environmental issues	*Long-term impact	x	*Long-term impact	x	*Long-term impact
	66	Improved communication and information exchange among stakeholders				x	
	67	Commitment from statutory agency to increase monitoring				x	
	68	Increased public acceptance and support for restoration				x	
	69	Sites for restoration identified				x	
70	Commitment for restoration by decision makers (including local municipality) incl. money & resources				x		
71	Increased awareness & acceptance of citizen scientists					x	
Long-Term Impacts	72	Increased recognition of the scientific role of secondary schools in environmental management			x		
	73	Greater bargaining capacity (with the regulatory agency) on the part of citizens			x		
	74	Increased evidence supporting effectiveness of NBS			x		
	75	Increased uptake of NBS			x		
	76	Increase confidence in science			x		

Item Type	IJM Item Number	IJM Item	Outfall Safari	Riverfly Monitoring Initiative	Marzenego River NBS project	Creek Rákos Citizen Science Project	Carasuhat Wetland NBS project
	77	Increased public awareness and knowledge of environmental issues	x	*Short-term impact	x	*Short-term impact	x
	78	Individual behaviour change			x		x
	79	Improved conservation (additional sites with protected status)				x	
	80	Improved environmental stewardship				x	
	81	Restoration implemented				x	
	82	Increased cooperation and/or collaboration between stakeholders			*Short-term impact	x	*Short-term impact
	83	Physical centre for sustainable exploitation of local resources established					x
	84	Controlled access for tourists - Mandatory local guides for large tourist groups and the creation of a local guidebook for good practices					x
	85	Improved national strategy for environmental protection developed by Ministry of Environment, Water and Forests					x
	86	Dedicated Management Plan for Carasuhat wetland					x
	87	New organization established for promoting and protecting Carasuhat Wetland					x
	88	Independent monitoring entity established to supervise newly created areas in the Danube Delta					x
	89	Improved stakeholder engagement in decision making regarding wetland management					x
	90	Improved living standards					x
	91	Improved scientific knowledge (e.g., increased evidence supporting effectiveness of NBS)		* Short-term impact	*Short-term impact		x
	92	Improved volunteer health	x				
	93	Improved Policies / Legislation	x				
	94	Improved decision making, e.g., regarding wetland management	x	x	x		
	95	Remediation of polluting outfalls	x				
	96	Changed policy priorities	x				
	97	Improved / diversified local economy	x				x
	98	Increased institutional knowledge in how to run effective citizen science project					*Short-term impact
	99	Community building	x	x	x		

Item Type	IJM Item Number	IJM Item	Outfall Safari	Riverfly Monitoring Initiative	Marzenego River NBS project	Creek Rákos Citizen Science Project	Carasuhát Wetland NBS project
	100	Improved ecosystem/ biophysical environment	x	x		x	x

Part B: Case Study Sites Evaluation

1. Outfall Safari, London, UK

1.1. Amendments to the Impact Monitoring Strategy for Outfall Safari

Table 2 shows the final IMS (v2) presented to the project managers (ZSL) responsible for managing Outfall Safari. An IMS for Outfall Safari was previously reported in D4.5 (IMS v1), several updates have been made to this following feedback from the project manager. These include:

- **Shared understanding of how to run effective citizen science activities.** Two indicators for this short-term impact were included in the original IMS: 1) '*number of publications (outputs from project)*', and 2) '*number of external citations*'. These indicators were created based on the assumption that academic publications were the primary medium via which the project shared insights regarding how to run effective citizen science activities with other citizen science practitioners. Upon consultation with the project manager this was indicated to not be the case, and the process is more informal. Instead, new understanding and insights are shared through informal conversations and/or formal presentations at conferences. This was therefore included as the primary indicator for the impact in v2 of the IMS, replacing the indicators '*number of publications (outputs from project)*' and '*number of external citations*'.
- **Increased public awareness and knowledge of environmental issues.** Five potential indicators were suggested as a means of assessing increased public awareness and knowledge of environmental issues, with three focusing on non-participants and two centred on participants (citizen scientists) involved in the project. However, engaging with non-participants can be difficult, and awareness raising is beyond the scope of the project funding. Implementation of the three indicators focused on non-participants would require, therefore, relying on project partners, i.e. Thames Water, who have funding for public awareness campaigns. This, however, was deemed to be unfeasible and the three indicators associated with non-participants were excluded from v2 of the IMS.

It was agreed that the impact would, instead, be assessed based on the indicators: '*number of people participated in training*' and, '*level of citizen scientist understanding regarding PSO (Polluting Surface Water Outfalls)*'. For the latter of these a questionnaire was created adopting elements of the state-of-the-art measures for knowledge gain developed by Braun & Dierkes (2019). As described in D2.7 (Wehn et al. 2021) these questions enable an assessment of citizen scientists environmental core knowledge, as well as knowledge relevant for achieving behavioural goals related to sustainability (which is often the desired outcome of a training or intervention).

- **Remediation of polluting surface water outfalls:** Previously this was a short-term impact and was reclassified as a long-term impact following feedback from the project manager.
- **Improved ecosystem/biophysical environment:** It was agreed to omit the indicator '*water Framework Directive (WFD) status of rivers*'. While measures taken to address PSWO undoubtedly improve urban river water quality this may not result in a change in their classification under the WFD, as other issues also impact their ecological status. A lack in visible progress, i.e. measures taken to address PSWO but no change in ecological status, may therefore cause fatigue amongst the citizen scientists / project managers.

Table 2. The IMS (v2) developed for the Outfall Safari citizen science project. Rows highlighted in RED are those indicators that were present in v1 of the IMS but have been omitted following discussion with the project manager; rows highlighted in LIGHT GREEN identify indicators for which are already being monitored, e.g., lists of prioritised outfalls are already collected to determine the number of outfalls prioritised. In the column **Implementation of IMS**: cells highlighted in DARK GREEN were implemented during the testing of the IMS; cells highlighted in YELLOW denote those indicators that require more time to collect the relevant information.

Impact Selected to Monitor		Monitoring scheme					Implementation of IMS
		Indicator	Method	Frequency	Responsibility - Who is involved	Feasibility	
Short-term impacts	Outfalls prioritised	List of prioritised outfalls	List of prioritised outfalls made available	Annually	Project managers	Feasible	
	Enhanced citizen scientist knowledge	Level of citizen scientist understanding regarding PSO AND generic environmental knowledge	Questionnaire to gauge level of understanding of citizen scientists currently involved	One-off activity	Project managers	Feasible	Questionnaire created (Annexe 3). Questionnaire has been circulated to citizens during two training events: preliminary results presented in Annexe 4.
			Questionnaire for new citizen scientists to gauge their level understanding before training	One-off activity before training			
			Questionnaire to gauge change in level of understanding over time	6-months – variable once surveys completed			
	Shared understanding of how to run effective citizen science activities	Number of publications (outputs from project)	Articles (likely) recorded already through dissemination tracking	Annually	Project managers	Feasible	
			Number of external citations				
		Number of new collaborative projects	Project managers self-reporting	Continually	Project managers	Feasible	
		Number of conferences and other events attend	Project managers self-reporting	Continually	Project managers	Feasible	
	Political pressure on local MPs, etc. and water companies and EA (by citizen scientists and wider public)	Number of communications to local MPs that have been taken up	Citizen scientists self-report	Annually	Citizen scientists	Feasible	
		Number of signatures to project endorsed campaigns/ petitions	Counts of signatures to campaigns / petitions	Variable - depends on frequency of petitions	Project managers	Feasible	
		Media coverage	Track media coverage	Continual*5	Project managers	Feasible	

Impact Selected to Monitor		Monitoring scheme					Implementation of IMS
		Indicator	Method	Frequency	Responsibility - Who is involved	Feasibility	
Long-term impacts	Remediation of polluting outfalls	Number of misconnections remedied	Water companies communicate number of outfalls fixed	Annually	Water company	Feasible	
	Increased public awareness and knowledge of environmental issues	Social media interaction(s)	Track social media (e.g., record number of tweets, posts, likes, etc.)	Continual	Project managers	Feasible	
		Interest in project - sign-up for newsletter etc.	Counts of interested people receiving communications	Continual	Project managers	Feasible	
		Number of people participated in training	Count of new volunteers signing up to be involved	Annually – at training events	Project managers	Feasible	
		Change in attitudes / awareness of polluting outfalls	Questionnaire designed to gauge public attitude toward PSO	Annually	Water company – Thames Water	Unclear	
		Level of citizen scientist understanding regarding PSO	Questionnaire to gauge level of understanding of citizen scientists currently involved	One-off activity	Project managers	Feasible	
				One-off activity before training			
	Annually						
	Improved ecosystem/biophysical environment	Number of misconnections remedied	Water companies communicate number of misconnections remedied	Annually	Project managers	Feasible	
		Water Framework Directive (WFD) status of rivers	Monitoring undertaken by other citizen science projects, e.g., Riverfly	Annually	Project managers	Feasible	
		Previously remediated outfalls remain non-polluting	Outfall Safari surveys	Every 4 years – completion	Project managers	Feasible	

Impact Selected to Monitor	Monitoring scheme					Implementation of IMS
	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Responsibility - Who is involved	Feasibility	
			of survey period			
Improved decision making regarding polluting outfalls	Institutional change (e.g., Thames Water - changed procedures, policies etc)	Retrospective questionnaires for Water Companies	Yearly	Project managers	Feasible	
		Change to annual company and other reports (e.g., annual management programme).	Yearly	Project manager	Feasible	
Improved Policies/Legislation	Number of communications to local MPs that have been taken up	Citizen scientists self-report	Annually	Citizen scientists	Feasible	
	Governmental policy change/written legislation	Policy/legislation search	Annually	Project managers	Feasible	

1.2. Implementation of the Outfall Safari Impact Monitoring Strategy

The IMS (Table 2) has been presented to the project manager of Outfall Safari who expressed an interest in its application. In Spring 2022 the IMS was trialled by the project manager who provided feedback on the process, ease of implementation and suggested changes to the IMS. Due to time constraints action was not taken for all the indicators. Those indicators for which information/actions were taken during this initial trial are highlighted in Dark Green in Table 1, while those indicators that will be implemented in the future are signified in Yellow.

Below are details regarding the implementation of the monitoring scheme for each of the impacts.

Short-Term Impacts

- **Outfalls prioritised.** Data for this is already collected as part of annual reporting.
- **Enhanced citizen scientist knowledge.** A questionnaire designed to measure environmental knowledge of citizen scientists before and after intervention was developed by the MICS team (see Annexe 3). This questionnaire was based on the framework outlined by Braun and Dierkes (2019) and enables measure of various areas of environmental knowledge (e.g., water, conservation, renewables, etc.). Further details regarding the framework developed by Braun and Dierkes (2019) can be found in Deliverable D2.7 (Wehn et al., 2021). The questionnaire was provided to new citizen scientists attending training events held in April 2022. Preliminary results from this can be found in Annexe 4. (Note no analysis has yet been undertaken due to low response rate, as of April 25th 3 respondents). Active citizen scientists will be invited to answer the questionnaire in Autumn 2022, following the end of the 2022 survey period.
- **Shared understanding of how to run effective citizen science activities.**
 - *Number of new collaborative projects.* Outfall Safari London is in the process of expanding its programme beyond the limits of London to include surrounding boroughs. Surveys from this expanded area will be part of the 2022 survey period. ZSL

is in consultation with another project hoping to apply the Outfall Safari method in late 2022.

- *Number of conferences and other events attend.* The Project manager is currently reviewing the number of past conferences attended where presentations relating to Outfall Safari were given. Going forward ZSL will keep track of any new conferences attended where results from Outfall Safari are presented.
- **Political pressure on local MPs, etc. and water companies and EA (by citizen scientists and wider public).** Not included in trial of IMS held in 2022. The project manager commented that the indicators suggested would provide useful information about how the project is having an impact on governance and policy but that data for these may be difficult to collect. It was suggested that an alternative indicator that could be incorporated within future iterations of scheme could be '*Number of times evidence from Outfall Safari is cited in governmental consultations*'.

Long-Term Impacts

- **Remediation of polluting outfalls.** A list of the number of remediated outfalls is compiled annually but permission is required from utilities company (Thames Water) to release these to citizens involved. The project manager is currently in conversations with Thames Water to make this information publicly available.
- **Increased public awareness and knowledge of environmental issues**
 - *Number of people participated in training.*
 - In 2021 approximately 100 volunteers took part in three Outfall Safari's in the Greater London Area. (This number may not be accurate, however, since training was held online rather than in person and attendance at subsequent training and survey events was lower than expected – exact numbers are difficult to quantify)
 - In 2022 two training events have taken place in April and a third is organised for later in the Summer
 - 52 new citizen scientists attended the training events held in April.
 - *Level of citizen scientist understanding regarding PSO.* The MICS team developed several questions to gauge citizen scientists' level of understanding regarding PSO. To avoid questionnaire fatigue, the questions were integrated within the questionnaire developed to gauge citizen science knowledge (see notes for **Enhanced citizen scientist knowledge**).
- **Improved ecosystem/biophysical environment**
 - *Number of misconnections remedied.*
 - Since the start of the Outfall Safari programme in 2016 569 outfalls with a combined score of >4 have been reported to Thames Water (100 of these were serious pollution events with a combined score of 10 or more out of 20).
 - Thames Water reported that there were 200 outfalls remedied by their Surface Water Outfall Programme (SWOP) team in the previous AMP period. The project manager is currently liaising with Thames Water to confirm how many of these were remediated as a result of the activities of the Outfall Safari Project.
 - *Previously remediated outfalls remain non-polluting.* Not included in trial of IMS held in 2022.

- **Improved decision-making regarding polluting outfalls.** Not included in trial of IMS held in 2022. The impact relates to institutional changes (changes in management, practices, procedures, and policies, etc.) within Thames Water that occur as a result of the activities of Outfall Safari. Monitoring these changes requires further discussion within representatives of Thames Water involved in the Outfall Safari project; ZSL is currently in discussion with these representatives to implement the indicators in the future.
- **Improved Policies/Legislation.** Not included in trial of IMS held in 2022. The impact is to be assessed based on two indicators: 1) '*number of communications to local MPs that have been taken up*' and 2) '*governmental policy change / written legislation*'. The former of these relies upon citizen scientists self-reporting any communications they may have MPs relating to PSWOs. The project manager felt that they required more time to discuss this further with participants involved in the project – ideally during the next annual meeting for the project – and to collate the information. The second indicator '*governmental policy change / written legislation*' similarly, required more time for the project manager to collect the relevant information (based on searches through policy and legislation).

2. Marzenego River, Venice, Italy

2.1. Amendments to the Impact Journey Map for the Marzenego River NBS Project

Several updates were made to the IJM for the Marzenego River NBS Project, these included:

Activities

- **Conduct monitoring activities.** Item added to synergise with other projects.
- **Environmental training/education.** Reclassified as an output (see below).

Outputs

- **Volunteers trained and equipped.** Formerly the activity 'environmental training/education' reclassified as an Output and reworded to standardise the phrasing for similar concepts used by MICS case study projects.
- **Baseline dataset established.** Minor rewording to better emphasise the establishment of a baseline dataset.
- **Network between different school groups established.** Added as an Output to fill a gap in the IJM.

Short-term impacts:

- **Improved relationships among stakeholders.** Reworded from '*increased connection between groups of active/sensitive citizens*'; this was deemed to be unclear.
- **Increased collaboration between different schools.** reworded from '*Increased connection between different school groups via joint projects*'.
- **Wider awareness of environmental issues.** Reworded from '*increased citizen awareness for environment*' to standardise the phrasing for similar concepts used by MICS case study projects.
- **Improved scientific knowledge:** reworded from '*increased (theoretical) knowledge*'.

Long-term impacts:

- **Increased public awareness and knowledge of environmental issues:** reworded from '*improved knowledge of freshwater ecosystems and NBS*'
- **Increased environmental database: removed as long-term impact.** Removed from the IJM

believed to be captured elsewhere, i.e., short-term impact *'Enhanced environmental database...'*

- **Increased evidence supporting effectiveness of NBS:** focus of original item unclear, 'Improved data interpretation', following discussion with project lead...

Finalised Impact Journey Map (IJM) for the Marzenego River NBS Project

Figure 1. The finalised IJM for the Marzenego River NBS Project. The lines connecting items have been coloured by the MICS team to indicate different types of causal relationships: solid purple lines indicate observed causal relationships, while dashed green lines represent expected causal relationships.

2.2. Impact Monitoring Strategy for the Marzenego River NBS Project

The IMS for the Marzenego NBS Project was created by MICS based on the impacts selected by stakeholders during the workshop. Table 3 details the monitoring scheme developed for the impacts selected.

Table 3. The IMS (v2) developed for the Marzenego River NBS Project. Rows highlighted in **RED** are those indicators that were present in v1 of the IMS but have been omitted following discussion with the project manager.

Impact Selected to Monitor		Monitoring scheme				
		Indicator	Method	Frequency	Responsibility - Who is involved	Feasibility
Short-Term Impacts	Wider awareness of environmental issues	Level of citizen scientist understanding regarding generic environmental knowledge	Questionnaire for new citizen scientists to gauge their level understanding before training	One-off activity before training	Project managers	Feasible
			Questionnaire to gauge change in level of understanding over time	Annually		
	Community building	Strength of community	Anecdotal evidence of community interactions / activities	Annually	Project manager	Feasible
	Enhanced citizen science knowledge	Level of citizen scientist understanding regarding generic environmental knowledge	Questionnaire for new citizen scientists to gauge their level understanding before training	One-off activity before training	Project manager	Feasible
			Questionnaire to gauge change in level of understanding over time	Annually		
	Increased cooperation and/or collaboration between stakeholders (authorities and citizen scientists)	Number of meetings, changes in types of channels & frequency of data and information flow between these stakeholders	Monitoring meeting agenda, (minutes) / anecdotal evidence	Annually	Project manager	Low feasibility
	Enhanced environmental databases / data coverage	Number of surveys submitted (per time unit) that are valid	Count number of surveys	Continually – however, report Yearly	Statutory agency Project manager	Feasible - extractable from digital system
		Number of surveys submitted (per time unit) that are valid	Count the number of sites with active volunteers and the length of time that records cover (should	Continually – however, report Yearly		Feasible

Impact Selected to Monitor		Monitoring scheme				
		Indicator	Method	Frequency	Responsibility - Who is involved	Feasibility
			already be recorded)			
		Number of new sites added (per time unit), old sites inactive on list	Count the number of new sites added to list	Yearly		
	Increased collaboration between different schools	Number of educational levels involved	Count number of educational levels	Yearly	School teachers	Feasible
		Number of schools	Count of number of schools involved			
		Number of pupils	Count of number of pupils involved			
Quantity and quality of interactions amongst stakeholders	Track interactions (anecdotal evidence)	Continually				
Long-Term Impacts	Increased public knowledge of environmental issues	Level of citizen scientist understanding environmental issues	Retrospective questionnaire for citizen scientists already involved	One off activity	Project manager	Feasible
				Annually - to record change over time		
			Questionnaire before and after training for new citizen scientists	Annually - at training event		
	Increased public awareness and knowledge of environmental issues	Level of citizen scientist understanding regarding generic environmental knowledge	Questionnaire for new citizen scientists to gauge their level understanding before training	One-off activity before training	Project manager	Feasible
				Questionnaire to gauge change in level of understanding over time		
	Individual behaviour change	Level of citizen scientist understanding regarding generic environmental knowledge	Questionnaire for new citizen scientists to gauge their level understanding before training	One-off activity before training	Project manager	Feasible
				Questionnaire to gauge change in level of understanding over time		
	Increased evidence supporting effectiveness of NBS	Number of incidents where results of citizen science activities are used to	Record, count and track the number of times data has been used	Annually	Project managers	Not currently feasible – requires future commitment / buy-in from

Impact Selected to Monitor	Monitoring scheme				
	Indicator	Method	Frequency	Responsibility - Who is involved	Feasibility
	inform management decision				environmental regulatory agency
Greater bargaining capacity (with the regulatory agency) on the part of citizens	Extra observations made by authorities, triggered by citizen science activities	Count of the number of extra sampling points added to	Annually	Project managers	Not currently feasible – requires future commitment / buy-in from environmental regulatory agency
	Number of incidents where citizen science activities have prompted regulatory agency action (e.g. site visit, remediation action, etc.)	Track and record number of event	Twice a year	Project managers	Feasible
Increased recognition of the scientific role of secondary schools in environmental management	New / existing methodology validated	Record instances where new / existing monitoring methodologies are validated	Annually	Project managers / school teachers	Feasible
	Number of collaborative projects with experts / environment agency	Count of number of collaborative projects established			

3. Creek Rákos, Budapest, Hungary

3.2. Amendments to the Impact Journey Map and Impact Monitoring Strategy for the Creek Rákos Citizen Science Project

- Figure 2 shows the IJM developed for the Rákos Citizen Science Project. No major changes were made to the IJM other than minor rewording to standardise similar concepts shared between the MICS case studies.
- Additionally, the connecting lines of the IJM were coloured to represent the different types of relationships that exists between the different IJM elements. As noted in D4.5 the lines connecting the items within the IJM represent relationships between these items. The colours represent:
 - Observed causal relationships (purple lines): e.g., activities that happen; outputs, outcomes impacts that are observed in Carasuhat Wetland NBS Project (but not always measured).
 - Expected causal relationships (dashed green lines): outcomes and impacts that are expected as a result of the project.
- No changes were made to the IMS for the case study.
- The project manager for the case study is currently reviewing the practicalities of implementing the IMS with key stakeholders engaged in the project.

Finalised Impact Journey Map (IJM) for the Creek Rákos Citizen Science Project

Figure 2. The finalised IJM for the Creek Rákos Citizen Science Project. No major changes have been made to the IJM presented in Deliverable D4.5 (Wheatland et al., 2021) other than the colouring of lines connecting items to indicate different types of causal relationships: solid purple lines indicate observed causal relationships, while dashed green lines represent expected causal relationships.

 Solid purple lines indicate observed causal relationships
 Dashed green lines represent expected causal relationships

4. Carasuhat Wetland, Danube Delta, Romania

4.1. Amendments to the Impact Journey Map for the Marzenego River NBS Project

- Figure 3 shows the IJM developed for the Carasuhat Wetland NBS project. Other than minor rewording to some of the elements of the IMS no significant changes have been made.
- As noted in D4.5 the lines connecting the items within the IJM represent relationships between these items. Here, these have been coloured to represent the different types of relationships that may exist:
 - Observed causal relationships (purple lines): e.g., activities that happen; outputs, outcomes impacts that are observed in Carasuhat Wetland NBS Project (but not always measured).
 - Expected causal relationships (dashed green lines): outcomes and impacts that are expected as a result of the project.

Finalised Impact Journey Map (IJM) for the Carasuhat Wetland NBS Project

Figure 3. The finalised IJM for the Carasuhat Wetland NBS Project. The lines connecting items have been coloured by the MICS team to indicate different types of causal relationships: solid purple lines indicate observed causal relationships, while dashed green lines represent expected causal relationships.

4.2. Impact Monitoring Strategy for the Carasuhat Wetland NBS Project

The IMS for the Carasuhat Wetland NBS Project was created by MICS based on the impacts selected by stakeholders during the workshop. Table 4 details the monitoring scheme developed for the impacts selected.

Table 4. IMS developed for the Carasuhat Wetland NBS Project.

Impact Selected to Monitor		Monitoring scheme				
		Indicator	Method	Frequency	Responsibility - Who is involved	Feasibility
Short-term impacts	Increased capacity within the DDBRA for data management	Number of employees working for DDBRA tasked with data management	Count of employees tasked with data management	Annually	DDBRA	Very feasible
	Improved communication and information exchange among stakeholders	Changes in communication paradigm (3 items)	Track interactions/ survey	Biannual	Project managers, other key stakeholders	Feasible
	Improved cooperation between stakeholders	Number of meetings, changes in types of channels & frequency of data and information flow between these stakeholders	Monitoring meeting agenda, (minutes)	Annual	Project managers	Low feasibility
		Quantity and quality of interactions amongst stakeholders	Track interactions	Continually	Project managers	Feasible
Long-term impacts	Physical Centre for Sustainable Exploitation of local resources established	Number of positive resolutions connected to the creation of a Centre for Sustainable Exploitation	Monitoring local decisions	Biannual	Project managers	Feasible
		Creation of Centre for Sustainable Exploitation	Centre established yes/no	One off	Project managers	Feasible
	Individual behaviour change (especially tourists)	Number of incident reports	Track number of incident reports submitted regarding poor behaviour, damage, etc.	Annually	Project managers	Feasible
		Change in attitudes / awareness of tourists	Questionnaires handed out by local tour operators?	Annually	Project managers	May be feasible – would require cooperation of tour operators
	Improved national strategy for environmental protection developed	Governmental Policy change / written legislation	Policy / legislation search	Yearly	Project managers	Feasible

Impact Selected to Monitor		Monitoring scheme				
		Indicator	Method	Frequency	Responsibility - Who is involved	Feasibility
	Mandatory local guides for large tourists group and the creation of a local guide book for good practices	Creation of a guidebook for local tour groups outlining good practice	Guidebooks created yes/no	One off	Project managers	Feasible
			Guidebook in use yes/no	Continually	Project managers	Feasible
	Improved decision making regarding wetland management	DDBRA – Number of incidents where results of citizen science activities are used to inform management decision	Record, count and track the number of times citizen science data has been used	Biannual	Project managers	Feasible

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Annexe 1: Questionnaire Gauging Citizen Scientists Perception of Nature

Citizen Scientist Questionnaire

Blues Spaces – including inland lakes, rivers, ponds, canals, and coastal environments – provide unique habitats for wildlife and have been shown to offer important benefits for human health and wellbeing. We – the MICS team – want to understand what your attitude towards Blue Spaces. MICS – Measuring the Impact of Citizen Science – is a European Union Horizon 2020 funded project that is developing methods and tools to evaluate the impact of citizen science activities in the development, implementation and monitoring of schemes to tackle environmental problems, such as river restoration. Your answers to the questions will help us with our understanding of people's environmental perceptions and with the development of impact assessment method for evaluating citizen science activities.

Section 1: Your Involvement in Citizen Science

Q1) What citizen science activities related to the MICS project are you involved in?

- Water quality*
- Habitat quality*
- Biodiversity*
- Flood risk*
- Other, please specify:*

Q2) Which of these activities do you prefer and why? (Please specify below).

Q3) Are you, or have you been involved in any other citizen science projects – past or present?

- No*
- Yes! Please specify:*

Q4) Has your involvement in citizen science helped you gain new scientific knowledge?

- No*
- Yes! Please specify:*

Q5) Would you like to continue to be involved in citizen science activities?

- Yes*
- No*
- Prefer not to say*

Section 2: Your Motivations

Q6) How has your involvement in citizen science activities directly benefited you? (Select all that apply).

- It allows me to do something I find fun and enjoy*
- I have an interest in scientific aspects of the project*
- There are financial rewards with being involved*

- I can obtain information/data for my own personal use*
- It has created career opportunities (e.g. via enhanced CV or contacts made)*
- Other, please specify:*

Q7) What have been the impacts has your involvement in citizen science? (Select all that apply). Rank these in the order of impact from 1 (not an impact) to 5 (significant impact).

<i>I have expanded my own personal knowledge and skills</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion
<i>I feel part of a community with a shared interest</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion
<i>I have been able to share my knowledge with others</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion
<i>I have gained a sense of achievement by doing something worthwhile</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion

Q8) What benefits do you believe your activities have on society? (Select all that apply).

- They contributes to the socio-economic development*
- They contributes to scientific knowledge*
- They contribute to environmental conservation*
- They help to influence decision making*
- Other, please specify:*

Section 3: Your Perception of Issues Related Blue Spaces

Citizen science can impact participants' perception of themselves, of science and their surrounding environment. We would like to understand your perception of Blue Spaces and the pressure they currently face.

Q9) In a year, how often do you visit Blue Spaces?

- Never*
- Hardly ever (less than once a year)*
- Rarely (a few times a year)*
- Sometimes (once a month)*
- Regularly (a couple of times a month)*
- Constantly (several times a week)*
- Not sure*

Q10) What types of recreational pursuits do you do when visiting Blue Spaces? (Select all that apply).

- Casual walking (including dog walking)*
- Water-based sports (canoeing, swimming, etc.)*
- Land-based sports (running, cycling, etc.)*
- Fishing*
- Wildlife watching*
- Other*
- None*

Q11) Do you feel that being involved in citizen science has encouraged you to visit Blue Spaces more often?

- Yes*
- No*
- Not sure*

Q12) In your opinion, what are the main problems affecting Blue Spaces where you live? Rank these in the order of impact from 1 (not an impact) to 5 (significant impact).

- | | | | | | | |
|---------------------------------------|---|---|---|---|---|------------|
| <i>Water pollution</i> | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | No opinion |
| <i>Rubbish/litter</i> | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | No opinion |
| <i>Poor habitat quality</i> | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | No opinion |
| <i>Too artificial</i> | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | No opinion |
| <i>Drought / water scarcity</i> | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | No opinion |
| <i>Poor facilities for recreation</i> | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | No opinion |
| <i>Overuse</i> | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | No opinion |
- Not sure*
 - Other, please specify:*

Q13) Rank each statement according to how well it fits your own opinion, where 1 is strongly disagree and 5 is strongly agree.

<i>River water quality is important to me</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion
<i>The presence of trees along river banks causes more problems than benefits</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion
<i>In the area I live, I am exposed to flood risk</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion
<i>Murky, sediment-rich water is a sign of an unhealthy river</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion
<i>A well-managed river should never flood</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion
<i>In-stream debris, such as dead wood, is beneficial to river habitats</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion
<i>The occasional flooding of fields next to rivers is a natural and desirable process</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion

Q14) In your opinion, why is it essential to protect Blue Spaces? (Select all that apply).

- For recreational activities*
- To protect the environment and wildlife*
- For tourism and related economic activities*
- For historical/cultural heritage*
- To provide services to surrounding regions (including flood protection)*
- Not sure*
- Other, please specify:*

Q15) In your opinion what improvements could be made to Blue Space in your area? (Select all that apply).

- No improvements needed*
- Restore natural habitat and processes*
- Improvements to landscape quality*
- Bank stabilization and engineering to prevent erosion or movement of the river*
- Cleaning or dredging of rivers for flood risk management*
- Not sure*
- Other, please specify:*

Q16) In your opinion does the general public have a role to play in river restoration projects?

- No, it is up to the authorities to decide what restoration works take place and to implement them*
- The general public should be able to help implement restoration projects planned by the authorities through volunteer groups*
- The general public should have the opportunity to participate in the decision-making process alongside the authorities to help decide what the aims and objectives of the restoration project will be, AND be able to help implement the restoration project through volunteer groups*
- Not sure*
- Other, please specify:*

Q17) Do you believe that citizen science has a positive impact on the management of Blue Spaces where you live?

- Yes*
- No*
- Not sure*

Q18) Have you been involved in any river restoration projects? If 'Yes' please describe your involvement.

- No*
- Yes! Please specify:*

Q19) Where do you receive information about environmental issues? (Select all that apply).

- Print media (newspapers, magazines, etc.)*
- Broadcast media (TV, radio)*
- Social media (blogs, image sharing and networking sites, etc.)*
- Word of mouth (friends, family, and acquaintances)*
- At school*
- Voluntary groups*
- Books*
- Events or public demonstrations*
- Other, please specify:*

Section 3: Your Background (Optional)

Citizen science attracts participants of all ages and from all walks of life. **The questions below are optional**, but will help us understand the diversity of people involved in citizen science activities.

Q20) To which gender do you identify as?

- Female*
- Male*
- Prefer not to say*
- Other, please specify:*

Q21) What is your age?

- Under 24 years old*
- 25-34 years old*
- 35-44 years old*
- 55-64 years old*
- 65-73 years old*
- 74 years old or older*
- Prefer not to say*

Q3) Where do you live?

ADJUST CASE-BY-CASE

Q22) What is the highest degree or level of education you have completed?

- No formal education*
- High school diploma*
- College degree*
- University degree (Bachelor's and Master's)*
- Doctorate degree*
- Professional degree*
- Prefer not to say*
- Other, please specify:*

Q23) Which of the following best describes your current employment status?

- Employed*

- Self-employed*
- Unemployed*
- Retired*
- Student*
- Prefer not to say*
- Other, please specify:*

Q24) Which of the following best describes your current occupation?

- Sales and retail*
- Business and financial operations*
- Legal*
- Architecture and engineering*
- Building and grounds cleaning and maintenance*
- Management*
- Personal care and services*
- Office and administrative support*
- Farming, fishing and forestry*
- Healthcare practitioners*
- Installation, maintenance, and repair*
- Food preparation and serving related*
- Production occupations*
- Healthcare support*
- Computer and mathematics*
- Construction and extraction*
- Community and social services*
- Education and training*
- Protective service*
- Arts, design, entertainment, sports, and media*
- Life, physical and social science*
- Transportation and materials moving*
- Other, please specify:*

Thank You for Taking Time to Answer Our Questions

The answers that you have provided will help us better understand what motivates people to be involved in citizen science and how their involvement influences their feelings towards the environment and scientific research in general.

We value your input and would like to share with you a summary of the results of this questionnaire with you. Would you like to hear about the results of this questionnaire?

- No*
- Yes! Please provide your email address below:*

Are you interested in being added to our mailing list to receive regular updates about the MICS project and the activities we run?

- No*
- Yes, add me to your mailing list! Please provide your email address below:*

Annexe 2: Results of the Survey Questionnaire Gauging Citizen Scientists Perception of Nature

Q1. What citizen science activities related to the MICS project are you involved in? (Select all that apply)

Answered: 7 Skipped: 1

<i>Answer Choices</i>	<i>Responses</i>	
Water quality monitoring	6	86%
Water level monitoring	7	100%
Bank stability monitoring	7	100%
Other, please specify:	1	14%

Response to 'other':

- The necessity of avoiding entering into the renatured area

Q2. Which of these activities do you prefer and why? (Please specify below).

Answered: 5 Skipped: 3

Responses:

- All
- I prefer water quality monitoring since it is a new activity in which I did not participate until now
- I consider that is imperative to know the quality of what we consume and if there is a problem to be able to rectify it
- Water quality monitoring
- Water level monitoring

Q3. Are you, or have you been involved in any other citizen science projects – past or present?

Answered: 8 Skipped: 0

<i>Answer Choices</i>	<i>Responses</i>	
No	7	88%
Yes! Please specify:	1	13%

Responses to 'yes':

- Renaturation project

Q4. Has your involvement in citizen science helped you gain new scientific knowledge?

Answered: 8 Skipped: 0

<i>Answer Choices</i>	<i>Responses</i>	
No	3	38%
Yes! Please specify:	5	63%

Responses to 'yes':

- Water quality
- Understanding water quality/parameters. Gaining new knowledge
- Surrounding water quality knowledge
- First of all it made me realize what the environmental problems are and made me see some of the ways that can solve them
- Specific water parameters

Q5) Would you like to continue to be involved in citizen science activities?

Answered: 8 Skipped: 0

<i>Answer Choices</i>	<i>Responses</i>	
Yes	8	100%
No	0	0%
Prefer not to say	0	0%

Q6) How has your involvement in citizen science activities directly benefited you? (Select all that apply).

Answered: 8 Skipped: 0

<i>Answer Choices</i>	<i>Responses</i>	
<i>It allows me to do something I find fun and enjoy</i>	5	63%
<i>I have an interest in scientific aspects of the project</i>	4	50%
<i>There are financial rewards with being involved</i>	0	0%
<i>I can obtain information/data for my own personal use</i>	4	50%
<i>It has created career opportunities (e.g. via enhanced CV or contacts made)</i>	2	25%
<i>Other, please specify:</i>	0	0%

Q7) What have been the impacts has your involvement in citizen science? (Select all that apply). Rank these in the order of impact from 1 (not an impact) to 5 (significant impact).

Answered: 8 Skipped: 0

<i>Opinions Related to Surface Water Outfalls</i>	<i>Rank</i>											
	<i>1 (Not an impact)</i>		<i>2</i>		<i>3</i>		<i>4</i>		<i>5 (Significant impact)</i>		<i>No opinion / Not sure</i>	
I have expanded my own personal knowledge and skills	0	0%	0	0%	2	25%	3	38%	3	38%	0	0%
I feel part of a community with a shared interest	0	0%	0	0%	1	13%	1	13%	6	75%	0	0%
I have been able to share my knowledge with others	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	3	38%	5	63%	0	0%
I have gained a sense of achievement by doing something worthwhile	0	0%	0	0%	1	13%	1	13%	6	75%	0	0%

Q8) What benefits do you believe your activities have on society? (Select all that apply).

Answered: 8 Skipped: 0

Answer Choices	Responses	
They contributes to the socio-economic development	6	75%
They contributes to scientific knowledge	6	75%
They contribute to environmental conservation	8	100%
They help to influence decision making	5	63%
Other, please specify:	0	0%

Q9) In a year, how often do you visit Blue Spaces?

Answered: 8 Skipped: 0

Answer	Responses	
Never	0	0%
Hardly ever (less than once a year)	0	0%
Rarely (a few times a year)	3	38%
Sometimes (once a month)	0	0%
Regularly (a couple of times a month)	3	38%
Constantly (several times a week)	2	25%
Not sure	0	0%

Q10) What types of recreational pursuits do you do when visiting Blue Spaces? (Select all that apply).

Answered: 8 Skipped: 0

<i>Answer</i>	<i>Responses</i>
<i>Casual walking (including dog walking)</i>	8
<i>Water-based sports (canoeing, swimming, etc.)</i>	2
<i>Land-based sports (running, cycling, etc.)</i>	4
<i>Fishing</i>	4
<i>Wildlife watching</i>	7
<i>Other</i>	0
<i>None</i>	0

Q11) Do you feel that being involved in citizen science has encouraged you to visit Blue Spaces more often?

Answered: 8 Skipped: 0

<i>Answer</i>	<i>Responses</i>
<i>Yes</i>	6 75%
<i>No</i>	1 13%
<i>Not sure</i>	1 13%

Q12) In your opinion, what are the main problems affecting Blue Spaces where you live? Rank these in the order of impact from 1 (not an impact) to 5 (significant impact).

Answered: 8 Skipped: 0

Opinions Related to Surface Water Outfalls	Rank											
	1 (Not an impact)		2		3		4		5 (Significant impact)		No opinion / Not sure	
Water pollution	0	0%	0	0%	3	38%	0	0%	5	63%	0	0%
Rubbish/litter	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	8	100%	0	0%
Poor habitat quality	5	63%	1	13%	0	0%	1	13%	0	0%	1	13%
Too artificial	5	63%	1	13%	1	13%	0	0%	0	0%	1	13%
Drought / water scarcity	1	13%	1	13%	1	13%	1	13%	4	50%	0	0%
Poor facilities for recreation	2	25%	0	0%	1	13%	2	25%	0	0%	3	38%
Overuse	1	13%	0	0%	4	50%	1	13%	1	13%	1	13%
Not sure	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
Other, please specify:	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%

Q13) Rank each statement according to how well it fits your own opinion, where 1 is strongly disagree and 5 is strongly agree.

Answered: 8 Skipped: 0

Opinions Related to Surface Water Outfalls	Rank											
	1 (Strongly disagree)		2		3		4		5 (Strongly agree)		No opinion / Not sure	
River water quality is important to me	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	2	25%	6	75%	0	0%
The presence of trees along river banks causes more problems than benefits	5	63%	1	13%	0	0%	0	0%	2	25%	0	0%
In the area I live, I am exposed to flood risk	4	50%	2	25%	0	0%	1	13%	1	13%	0	0%
Murky, sediment-rich water is a sign of an unhealthy river	1	13%	4	50%	0	0%	1	13%	2	25%	0	0%
A well-managed river should never flood	4	50%	0	0%	0	0%	2	25%	0	0%	2	25%
In-stream debris, such as dead wood, is beneficial to river habitats	2	25%	1	13%	1	13%	1	13%	2	25%	1	13%
The occasional flooding of fields next to rivers is a natural and desirable process	1	13%	2	25%	2	25%	1	13%	1	13%	1	13%

Q14) In your opinion, why is it essential to protect Blue Spaces? (Select all that apply).

Answered: 8 Skipped: 0

Answer	Responses	
For recreational activities	7	88%
To protect the environment and wildlife	8	100%
For tourism and related economic activities	8	100%
For historical/cultural heritage	5	63%
To provide services to surrounding regions (including flood protection)	5	63%
Not sure	0	0%
Other, please specify:	0	0%

Q15) In your opinion what improvements could be made to Blue Space in your area? (Select all that apply).

Answered: 8 Skipped: 0

Answer	Responses	
No improvements needed	0	0%
Restore natural habitat and processes	4	50%
Improvements to landscape quality	5	63%
Bank stabilization and engineering to prevent erosion or movement of the river	8	100%
Cleaning or dredging of rivers for flood risk management	7	88%
Not sure	0	0%
Other, please specify:	0	0%

Q16) In your opinion does the general public have a role to play in river restoration projects?

Answered: 8 Skipped: 0

<i>Answer</i>	<i>Responses</i>	
<i>No, it is up to the authorities to decide what restoration works take place and to implement them</i>	1	13%
<i>The general public should be able to help implement restoration projects planned by the authorities through volunteer groups</i>	6	75%
<i>The general public should have the opportunity to participate in the decision-making process alongside the authorities to help decide what the aims and objectives of the restoration project will be, AND be able to help implement the restoration projects</i>	6	88%
<i>Not sure</i>	0	0%
<i>Other, please specify:</i>	0	0%

Q17) Do you believe that citizen science has a positive impact on the management of Blue Spaces where you live?

Answered: 8 Skipped: 0

<i>Answer</i>	<i>Responses</i>	
<i>Yes</i>	8	100%
<i>No</i>	0	0%
<i>Not sure</i>	0	0%

Q18) Have you been involved in any river restoration projects? If 'Yes' please describe your involvement.

Answered: 8 Skipped: 0

<i>Answer</i>	<i>Responses</i>	
<i>No</i>	4	50%
<i>Yes! Please specify</i>	4	50%

Responses:

- Participant

Q19) Where do you receive information about environmental issues? (Select all that apply).

Answered: 8 Skipped: 0

Answer	Responses
Print media (newspapers, magazines, etc.)	4
Broadcast media (TV, radio)	6
Social media (blogs, image sharing and networking sites, etc.)	7
Word of mouth (friends, family, and acquaintances)	7
At school	3
Voluntary groups	4
Books	2
Events or public demonstrations	3
Other, please specify:	1

Responses:

- Telephonic connection with the people that are involved

Q20) To which gender do you identify as?

Answered: 7 Skipped: 1

Answer	Responses
Female	5
Male	2
Prefer not to say	0
Other, please specify:	0

Q21) What is your age?

Answered: 6 Skipped: 2

Answer	Responses	
Under 24 years old	1	17%
25-34 years old	0	0%
35-44 years old	1	17%
45-54 years old	3	50%
55-64 years old	0	0%
65-73 years old	1	17%
74 years old or older	0	0%
Prefer not to say	0	0%

Q22) Where do you live?

Answered: 8 Skipped: 0

Answer	Responses
Mahmudia	7
Tulcea	1

Q23) What is the highest degree or level of education you have completed?

Answered: 7 Skipped: 1

Answer	Responses	
No formal education	0	0%
High school diploma	2	29%
College degree	0	0%
University degree (Bachelor's and Master's)	4	57%
Doctorate degree	0	0%
Professional degree	1	14%
Prefer not to say	0	0%
Other, please specify:	0	0%

Q24) Which of the following best describes your current employment status?

Answered: 6 Skipped: 2

Answer	Responses	
Employed	4	67%
Self-employed	1	16%
Unemployed	0	0%
Retired	0	0%
Student	0	0%
Prefer not to say	0	0%
Other, please specify:	1	17%

Responses:

- Tourism

Q25) Which of the following best describes your current occupation?

Answered: 5 Skipped: 3

Answer	Responses	
Sales and retail	0	0%
Business and financial operations	0	0%
Legal	0	0%
Architecture and engineering	0	0%
Building and grounds cleaning and maintenance	0	0%
Management	1	17%
Personal care and services	0	0%
Office and administrative support	2	33%
Farming, fishing and forestry	0	0%
Healthcare practitioners	0	0%
Installation, maintenance, and repair	0	0%
Food preparation and serving related	0	0%
Production occupations	0	0%
Healthcare support	0	0%
Computer and mathematics	0	0%
Construction and extraction	0	0%

- Management
- Education and training
- Transportation and materials moving
- Other, please specify:

<i>Community and social services</i>	0	0%	
<i>Education and training</i>	2	33%	
<i>Protective service</i>	0	0%	
<i>Arts, design, entertainment, sports, and media</i>	0	0%	
<i>Life, physical and social science</i>	0	0%	
<i>Transportation and materials moving</i>	0	0%	
<i>Other, please specify:</i>	1	17%	

Responses (Other):

- Person transport on the Danube

Annexe 3: Questionnaire Gauging Knowledge Citizen Scientists Regarding Environmental Issues

Understanding Knowledge Gain Through Involvement in Citizen Science

Misconnected pipes are a major threat to water quality in urban rivers. These send untreated wastewater directly to rivers via the surface water drainage system and compromise the biodiversity and amenity value of our waterways. Outfall Safari is a citizen science method for locating, assessing the impact of, and reporting polluted surface water outfalls. Outfall Safari has been responsible for helping to drive improvement in urban water quality across the country, but this is only possible with the support and interest of citizen scientists.

We – the MICS team – want to know how your involvement in citizen science projects (like Outfall Safari) influences your understanding of issues in rivers and our wider environment. MICS – Measuring the Impact of Citizen Science – is a European Union Horizon 2020 funded project that is developing methods and tools to evaluate the impact of citizen science activities in the development, implementation, and monitoring of schemes to tackle environmental problems, such as river restoration. Your answers to the questions will help us understand how people’s knowledge of wider environmental issues changes through being involved in citizen science projects.

Section 1: Your Involvement in Outfall Safari

Q1) Are you a new volunteer yet to receive training for Outfall Safari or an active volunteer currently involved in the project?

- I am a new volunteer (skip Q2 – Q4 and proceed to Section 2)*
- I am an active Outfall Safari volunteer (continue to next question)*

Q2) If you are an active Outfall Safari volunteer, how long have you been involved in Outfall Safari?

- <1 year*
- 1-2 years*
- 2-3 years*

- >4 years

Q3) If you are a new volunteer joining Outfall Safari, please share with us why you joined. (Select all that apply).

- Interested in the topic
- To learn and do something new
- To spend time 'in nature'
- To meet new people
- Desire to volunteer
- Contribute to science
- Feels important to help

Q4) For each statement, please indicate to what extent you agree with it, where 1 is strongly disagree and 5 is strongly agree.

My involvement in Outfall Safari has helped me to expand my own personal knowledge and skills 1 2 3 4 5 No opinion/Not sure

I have been shared the knowledge I have gained through being involved with Outfall Safari with others 1 2 3 4 5 No opinion/Not sure

My involvement in Outfall Safari has made me more aware of the issues that impact river health 1 2 3 4 5 No opinion/Not sure

By being involved in Outfall Safari I have gained a sense of achievement by doing something worthwhile 1 2 3 4 5 No opinion/Not sure

Other, please if there are any additional benefits of being involved in Outfall Safari:

Section 2: Your Knowledge and Understanding of the Issues Related to Rivers

Q5) Rank each statement related to surface water outfalls according to how well it fits your own opinion, where 1 is strongly disagree and 5 is strongly agree.

I understand how surface water outfalls become polluted 1 2 3 4 5 No opinion/Not sure

<i>I can identify a polluting surface water outfall</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion/Not sure
<i>I feel that my actions as an Outfall Safari volunteer will help/have helped to tackle river pollution</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion/Not sure
<i>Do you know how the results from your outfall observation are used?</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion/Not sure

Q6) In your opinion, what are the main problems affecting rivers? Please score these issues according to the degree of impact you believe they have on river health, from 1 (has no impact) to 5 (has significant impact).

<i>Domestic pollution caused by incorrectly plumbed drainage</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion/Not sure
<i>Rubbish/litter</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion/Not sure
<i>Poor in-channel habitat quality</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion/Not sure
<i>Too artificial, e.g., the channel has been straightened, reinforced with concrete etc.</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion/Not sure
<i>Loss of terrestrial habitat adjacent to rivers, i.e. riparian corridor and floodplain</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion/Not sure
<i>Water scarcity due to drought / over abstraction</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion/Not sure
<i>Poor facilities for recreation</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion/Not sure
<i>Overuse</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion/Not sure

Other, please specify:

Q7) Rank each statement according to how well it fits your own opinion, where 1 is strongly disagree and 5 is strongly agree.

<i>River water quality is important to me</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion/Not sure
<i>The presence of trees along river banks causes more problems than benefits</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion/Not sure
<i>In the area I live, I am exposed to flood risk</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion/Not sure
<i>Murky, sediment-rich water is a sign of an unhealthy river</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion/Not sure
<i>A well-managed river should never flood</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion/Not sure

<i>In-stream debris, such as dead wood, is beneficial to river habitats</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion/Not sure
<i>The occasional flooding of fields next to rivers is a natural and desirable process</i>	1	2	3	4	5	No opinion/Not sure

Q8) In your opinion, why is it essential to protect rivers? (Select all that apply).

- For recreational activities*
- To protect the environment and wildlife*
- For tourism and related economic activities*
- For historical/cultural heritage*
- To provide services to surrounding regions (including flood protection)*
- Not sure*
- Other, please specify:*

Q9) Do you know of any other citizen science projects that seek to improve river health?

- No*
- Yes, please specify:*

Q10) Are you involved in any other citizen science projects?

- No*
- Yes, please specify:*

Section 3: Your Knowledge and Understanding of Wider Environmental Issues

Q11) Deforestation causes... (select all that apply)

- A change in the amount of rainfall*
- Destruction of habitats*
- A dryer and hotter climate*
- More fertile ground*

Q12) Which of the following is the reason for the greenhouse effect? (select all that apply)

- The proceeding destruction of the ozone layer*
- Increased vegetation on earth*
- Increased amount of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere*
- The melting of the polar ice caps*

Q13) Which of these products do not contain palm oil? (Select all that apply)

- Paper*
- Soap*
- Chocolate*
- Cosmetics*

Q14) Which are coniferous trees? (Select all that apply)

- Beech Tree*
- Douglas fir*
- Palm tree*
- Spruce*

Q15) What can contribute to the conservation of plants and animals? (Select all that apply)

- Feeding birds in the park with bread*
- Buying sustainable products (e.g. wood with the FSC seal)*
- Buying products of endangered species (e.g. ivory)*
- Planting native vegetation in the garden*

Q16) You can minimise energy consumption by... (select all that apply)

- Wasting less warm water*
- Using the air conditioning on a high level*

- Turning off the lights when leaving a room*
- Leaving electric devices on standby mode*

Q17) What belongs in a sustainable shopping basket? (Select all that apply)

- Seasonal and regional products*
- Convenience food*
- Organic food*
- Imported goods*

Q18) How can you contribute to a healthy environment (select all that apply)

- Washing clothes less often*
- Using public transport*
- Using plastic cups*
- Eating more meat*

Q19) How much water can be saved by taking a shower instead of a bath? (Select all that apply)

- Up to 500 litres*
- Up to 120 litres*
- Up to 70 litres*
- Up to 30 litres*

Q20) By using which kind of bottle do you damage the environment the most? (Select all that apply)

- Single use glass bottles*
- Reusable glass bottles*
- Single use plastic bottles*
- Reusable plastic bottles*

Q21) By avoiding which food(s) can you save the most greenhouse gases? (Select all that apply)

- Fruits and vegetables*
- Meat*
- Bread and rice*
- Sweets*

Q22) How much electricity can be saved by using an energy-saving bulb instead of a conventional bulb? (Select all that apply)

- Up to 10%*

- Up to 20%*
- Up to 30%*
- Up to 40%*

Section 3: Your Background (Optional)

Outfall Safari attracts participants of all ages and from all walks of life. **The questions below are optional** but will help us understand the diversity of people involved in Outfall Safari.

Q23) Which gender do you identify as?

- Female*
- Male*
- Prefer not to say*
- Other, please specify:*

Q24) What is your age?

- Under 24 years old*
- 25-34 years old*
- 35-44 years old*
- 45-54 years old*
- 55-64 years old*
- 65-73 years old*
- 74 years old or older*
- Prefer not to say*

Q25) What is the highest degree or level of education you have completed?

- No formal education*
- High school diploma*
- College degree*
- University degree (Bachelor's and Master's)*
- Doctorate degree*

- Professional degree*
- Prefer not to say*
- Other, please specify:*

Q26) Which of the following best describes your current employment status?

- Employed*
- Self-employed*
- Unemployed*
- Retired*
- Student*
- Prefer not to say*
- Other, please specify:*

Q27) Which of the following best describes your current occupation?

- Sales and retail*
- Business and financial operations*
- Legal*
- Architecture and engineering*
- Building and grounds cleaning and maintenance*
- Management*
- Personal care and services*
- Office and administrative support*
- Farming, fishing and forestry*
- Healthcare practitioners*
- Installation, maintenance, and repair*
- Food preparation and serving related*

- Production occupations*
- Healthcare support*
- Computer and mathematics*
- Construction and extraction*
- Community and social services*
- Education and training*
- Protective service*
- Arts, design, entertainment, sports, and media*
- Life, physical and social science*
- Transportation and materials moving*
- Other, please specify:*

Thank You for Taking Time to Answer Our Questions

The answers that you have provided will help us better understand what motivates people to be involved in citizen science and how their involvement influences their feelings towards the environment and scientific research in general.

This questionnaire was developed by the Measuring the Impact of Citizen Science (MICS) project. MICS is a European Union Horizon 2020 funded project that is developing methods and tools to evaluate the impact of citizen science activities in the development, implementation and monitoring of schemes to tackle environmental problems, such as river restoration. Your answers to the questions will help us with our understanding of people's environmental perceptions and with the development of impact assessment methods for evaluating citizen science activities. You can find out more information about the MICS project by visiting our website <https://mics.tools/>, or following us on social media <https://twitter.com/MICSproject>.

Annexe 4: Answers from Questionnaire Gauging Citizen Scientists Knowledge Regarding Environmental Issues

Q1) Are you a new volunteer yet to receive training for Outfall Safari or an active volunteer currently involved in the project?

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Q2) If you are an active Outfall Safari volunteer, how long have you been involved in Outfall Safari?

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Q3) If you are a new volunteer joining Outfall Safari, please share with us why you joined. (Select all that apply).

Answered: 1 Skipped: 2

Q4) For each statement, please indicate to what extent you agree with it, where 1 is strongly disagree and 5 is strongly agree.

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Opinions as to How Involvement in Outfall Safari has Affected Citizen Scientists	Rank											
	1		2		3		4		5		No opinion / Not sure	
<i>My involvement in Outfall Safari has helped me to expand my own personal knowledge and skills</i>	0	0%	0	0%	2	67%	1	33%	0	0%	0	0%
<i>I have been shared the knowledge I have gained through being involved with Outfall Safari with others</i>	0	0%	0	0%	1	33%	1	33%	1	33%	0	0%
<i>My involvement in Outfall Safari has made me more aware of the issues that impact river health</i>	0	0%	0	0%	1	33%	1	33%	1	33%	0	0%
<i>By being involved in Outfall Safari I have gained a sense of achievement by doing something worthwhile</i>	0	0%	0	0%	1	33%	1	33%	1	33%	0	0%

Responses to 'other' additional benefits of being involved in Outfall Safari:

- Awareness of nature around you
- It has encouraged me to learn more about river health and take part in other citizen science projects such as riverfly monitoring

Q5) Rank each statement related to surface water outfalls according to how well it fits your own opinion, where 1 is strongly disagree and 5 is strongly agree.

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Opinions Related to Surface Water Outfalls	Rank										No opinion / Not sure	
	1		2		3		4		5			
<i>I understand how surface water outfalls become polluted</i>	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0	3	100%	0	0%
<i>I can identify a polluting surface water outfall</i>	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	1	33	2	67%	0	0%
<i>I feel that my actions as an Outfall Safari volunteer will help/have helped to tackle river pollution</i>	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	2	67	1	33%	0	0%
<i>Do you know how the results from your outfall observation are used?</i>	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	3	100%	0	0%	0	0%

Q6) In your opinion, what are the main problems affecting rivers? Please score these issues according to the degree of impact you believe they have on river health, from 1 (has no impact) to 5 (has significant impact).

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Problems Affecting Rivers	Rank										No opinion / Not sure	
	1		2		3		4		5			
Domestic pollution caused by incorrectly plumbed drainage	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	2	67%	1	33%	0	0%
Rubbish/litter	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	2	67%	1	33%	0	0%
Poor in-channel habitat quality	0	0%	0	0%	2	67%	1	33%	0	0%	0	0%
Too artificial, e.g., the channel has been straightened, reinforced with concrete etc.	0	0%	1	0%	0	0%	1	0%	1	0%	0	0%
Loss of terrestrial habitat adjacent to rivers, i.e. riparian corridor and floodplain	0	0%	0	0%	2	67%	1	33%	0	0%	0	0%
Water scarcity due to drought / over abstraction	1	33%	0	0%	0	0%	2	67%	0	0%	0	0%
Poor facilities for recreation	1	33%	1	33%	1	33%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
Overuse	1	33%	1	33%	0	0%	1	33%	0	0%	0	0%

Responses to 'other' problems identified affecting rivers:

- Agricultural runoff, both fertilisers and animals medicines - hormones and antibiotics. Runoff from over-fertilised urban gardens. Dog flea collars, especially in pristine rural places. Climate Change and increased rainfall overloading Victorian sewers. Poor planning permission decisions on housebuilding and impervious paved surfaces.
- Sewage discharge from water treatment plants, road run off, wastewater containing oil/chemicals from commercial premises, agricultural run-off

Q7) Rank each statement according to how well it fits your own opinion, where 1 is strongly disagree and 5 is strongly agree.

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Opinions regarding issues related to freshwater environments	Rank											
	1		2		3		4		5		No opinion / Not sure	
River water quality is important to me	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	3	100%	0	0%
The presence of trees along river banks causes more problems than benefits	2	67%	1	33%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
In the area I live, I am exposed to flood risk	2	67%	1	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
Murky, sediment-rich water is a sign of an unhealthy river	1	33%	1	33%	1	33%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
A well-managed river should never flood	1	33%	1	33%	1	33%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
In-stream debris, such as dead wood, is beneficial to river habitats	0	0%	2	67%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	1	33%
The occasional flooding of fields next to rivers is a natural and desirable process	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	1	33%	1	33%	1	33%

Q8) In your opinion, why is it essential to protect rivers? (Select all that apply).

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

<i>Answer</i>	<i>Responses</i>	
No	0	0
Yes, please specify:	3	100

Responses to 'other' reasons why it is essential to protect rivers:

- Protecting our water supply and reducing the cost of treating it.

Q9) Do you know of any other citizen science projects that seek to improve river health?

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

<i>Answer</i>	<i>Responses</i>	
No	0	0
Yes, please specify:	3	100

Response:

- ObstacleEELS. Anglers Riverfly Monitoring Initiative (ARMI) and other Riverfly Partnership RMIs, Eel Monitoring and Smelt fishery monitoring (ZSL)
- Riverfly
- Angler riverfly monitoring initiative

Q10) Are you involved in any other citizen science projects?

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

<i>Answer</i>	<i>Responses</i>	
No	0	0
Yes, please specify:	3	100

Response:

- Ravensbourne RMI. ObstacleEELS. Smelt egg monitoring and Smelt Fishermen.
- Riverfly
- Angler riverfly monitoring initiative, UK butterfly monitoring scheme

Q11) Deforestation causes... (select all that apply)

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Participants	A change in the amount of rainfall	Destruction of habitats	A dryer and hotter climate	More fertile ground	Participant score
1	1	1	1	1	P
2	1	1	1	0	ü
3	1	1	1	0	ü
% of participants that selected response	100%	100%	100%	33%	

*Correct answers indicated in bold and highlighted in blue. Correct = ü, Partially Correct = P, Incorrect = x.

Q12) Which of the following is the reason for the greenhouse effect? (select all that apply)

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Participants	The proceeding destruction of the ozone layer	Increased vegetation on earth	Increased amount of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere	The melting of the polar ice caps	Participant score
1	1	1	1	1	P
2	1	1	1	0	ü
3	1	1	1	0	ü
% of participants that selected response	100%	100%	100%	33%	

*Correct answers indicated in bold and highlighted in blue. Correct = ü, Partially Correct = P, Incorrect = x.

Q13) Which of these products do not contain palm oil? (Select all that apply)

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Participants	Paper	Soap	Chocolate	Cosmetics	Participant score
1	0	0	1	0	ü
2	1	0	1		P
3	1	0	1	0	P
% of participants that selected response	67%	0%	100%	0%	

*Correct answers indicated in bold and highlighted in blue. Correct = ü, Partially Correct = P, Incorrect = x.

Q14) Which are coniferous trees? (Select all that apply)

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Participants	Beech Tree	Douglas fir	Palm tree	Spruce	Participant score
1	1	0	0	0	ü
2	0	1	1	1	x
3	1	0	0	0	ü
% of participants that selected response	67%	33%	33%	33%	

*Correct answers indicated in bold and highlighted in blue. Correct = ü, Partially Correct = P, Incorrect = x.

Q15) What can contribute to the conservation of plants and animals? (Select all that apply)

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Participants	Feeding birds in the park with bread	Buying sustainable products (e.g. wood with the FSC seal)	Buying products of endangered species (e.g. ivory)	Planting native vegetation in the garden	Participant score
1	0	1	0	1	P
2	0	1	0	1	P
3	0	1	1	1	ü
% of participants that selected response	0%	100%	33%	100%	

*Correct answers indicated in bold and highlighted in blue. Correct = ü, Partially Correct = P, Incorrect = x.

Q16) You can minimise energy consumption by... (select all that apply)

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Participants	Wasting less warm water	Using the air conditioning on a high level	Turning off the lights when leaving a room	Leaving electric devices on standby mode	Participant score
1	1	0	1	0	ü
2	1	0	1	1	P
3	1	0	1	0	ü
% of participants that selected response	100%	0%	100%	33%	

*Correct answers indicated in bold and highlighted in blue. Correct = ü, Partially Correct = P, Incorrect = x.

Q17) What belongs in a sustainable shopping basket? (Select all that apply)

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Participants	Seasonal and regional products	Convenience food	Organic food	Imported goods	Participant score
1	1	0	0	0	P
2	1	0	1	0	ü
3	1	0	1	0	ü
% of participants that selected response	100%	0%	67%	0%	

*Correct answers indicated in bold and highlighted in blue. Correct = ü, Partially Correct = P, Incorrect = x.

Q18) How can you contribute to a healthy environment (select all that apply)

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Participants	Washing clothes less often	Using public transport	Using plastic cups	Eating more meat	Participant score
1	1	1	0	0	ü
2	1	1	0	0	ü
3	1	1	0	0	ü
% of participants that selected response	100%	100%	0%	0%	

*Correct answers indicated in bold and highlighted in blue. Correct = ü, Partially Correct = P, Incorrect = x.

Q19) How much water can be saved by taking a shower instead of a bath? (Select all that apply)

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Participants	Up to 500 litres	Up to 120 litres	Up to 70 litres	Up to 30 litres	Participant score
1	0	0	0	1	x
2	0	0	0	1	x
3	0	0	1	1	P
% of participants that selected response	0%	0%	33%	100%	

*Correct answers indicated in bold and highlighted in blue. Correct = ü, Partially Correct = P, Incorrect = x.

Q20) By using which kind of bottle do you damage the environment the most? (Select all that apply)

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Participants	Single use glass bottles	Reusable glass bottles	Single use plastic bottles	Reusable plastic bottles	Participant score
1	1	0	1	0	P
2	0	0	1	1	P
3	1	0	1	0	P
% of participants that selected response	67%	0%	100%	33%	

*Correct answers indicated in bold and highlighted in blue. Correct = ü, Partially Correct = P, Incorrect = x.

Q21) By avoiding which food(s) can you save the most greenhouse gases? (Select all that apply)

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Participants	Fruits and vegetables	Meat	Bread and rice	Sweets	Participant score
1	0	1	0	0	ü
2	0	1	0	1	P
3	0	1	0	0	x
% of participants that selected response	0%	100%	0%	33%	

*Correct answers indicated in bold and highlighted in blue. Correct = ü, Partially Correct = P, Incorrect = x.

Q22) How much electricity can be saved by using an energy-saving bulb instead of a conventional bulb? (Select all that apply)

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Participants	Up to 10%	Up to 20%	Up to 30%	Up to 40%	Up to 50%	Up to 80%	Participant score
1	0	0	0	1	0	0	x
2	0	0	0	1	0	0	x
3	0	0	0	1	0	0	x
% of participants that selected response	0%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	

*Correct answers indicated in bold and highlighted in blue. Correct = ü, Partially Correct = P, Incorrect = x.

Q23) Which gender do you identify as?

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Answer	Responses	
Female	2	66%
Male	1	33%
Prefer not to say	0	0%
Other, please specify:	0	0%

Q24) What is your age?

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Answer	Responses	
Under 24 years old	0	0%
25-34 years old	0	0%
35-44 years old	0	0%
45-54 years old	0	0%
55-64 years old	2	67%
65-73 years old	1	33%
74 years old or older	0	0%
Prefer not to say	0	0%

Q25) What is the highest degree or level of education you have completed?

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Answer	Responses	
No formal education	0	0%
High school diploma	0	0%
College degree	0	0%
University degree (Bachelor's and Master's)	3	100%
Doctorate degree	0	0%
Professional degree	0	0%
Prefer not to say	0	0%
Other, please specify:	0	0%

Q26) Which of the following best describes your current employment status?

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Answer	Responses	
Employed	1	33%
Self-employed	1	34%
Unemployed	0	0%
Retired	1	33%
Student	0	0%
Prefer not to say	0	0%
Other, please specify:	0	0%

Q27) Which of the following best describes your current occupation?

Answered: 3 Skipped: 0

Answer	Responses	
Sales and retail	0	0%
Business and financial operations	1	33%
Legal	0	0%
Architecture and engineering	0	0%
Building and grounds cleaning and maintenance	0	0%
Management	0	0%
Personal care and services	0	0%
Office and administrative support	0	0%
Farming, fishing and forestry	0	0%
Healthcare practitioners	0	0%
Installation, maintenance, and repair	0	0%
Food preparation and serving related	0	0%
Production occupations	0	0%
Healthcare support	0	0%
Computer and mathematics	0	0%
Construction and extraction	0	0%
Community and social services	0	0%
Education and training	0	0%
Protective service	0	0%
Arts, design, entertainment, sports, and media	0	0%
Life, physical and social science	0	0%
Transportation and materials moving	0	0%
Other, please specify:	2	67%

Response to 'Other' occupation:

- Waste management and recycling
- Wildlife Veterinary Medicine